

Chemical Investigation of *Azadirachta indica* Leaf (*M. Azadirachta*)

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In connection with the systematic studies on some members of Meliaceae, we were interested to examine the leaves of *Azadirachta indica*² (Syn. *Melia azadirachta*). The taxonomic closeness of the family *Rutaceae* and *Meliaceae* are also reflected in their flavonoid constituents. Besides nimbine^{3,4,5,6} and other bitter constituents isolated from the different parts of *Azadirachta indica*, kaempferol⁷ has been reported from the flowers of the plant. We now report the isolation of quercetin and β -sitosterol from the leaves of *Azadirachta indica*.

The phenolic fraction of the petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the leaves of *Azadirachta indica* on crystallisation from alcohol furnished a yellow compound C₁₅H₁₀O₇*, m.p. 295-305°, which on purification melted at 310-15°. The compound C₁₅H₁₀O₇ reacted with magnesium powder and hydrochloric acid like flavonoids. It was homogeneous by paper chromatography (R_f 0.73 in n-butanol: acetic acid: water::4:1:5). The uv. spectrum of the compound showed absorption max at 254 m μ (log ϵ 4.32) and 269 m μ (log ϵ 4.3) respectively. On acetylation with pyridine and acetic anhydride the compound gave an acetate, C₂₅H₂₀O₁₂*, m.p. 199-200°. The identity of the compound with quercetin was confirmed by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and paper co-chromatography).

The neutral fraction of the above extract on chromatography over alumina furnished a compound, C₂₉H₅₀O*, m.p. 135-37°, [α]_D(CHCl₃)-35° which responded to positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction showing it to be a sterol. The compound was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.p. and m.m.p.). Like β -sitosterol it furnished an acetate on acetylation in pyridine and acetic anhydride, C₃₁H₅₂O₂*, m.p. 130-133°, [α]_D-39° and m.m.p. with β -sitosterol acetate 130-33°.

The use of the leaves of the plant in sores and scabies is interesting from the stand point of its antibiotic activity, as quercetin is known to have antibacterial and antifungal action⁸.

*Satisfactory analysis were obtained.

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